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Real time robot arm collision detection and path planning

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Collaborative robots are intended to create a manufacturing workplace where humans can share a commonplace with the machines and work together. Unfortunately, most workplaces have yet to allow real collaboration between them. In most cases, even collaborative robots are isolated from human contact because of safety requirements. Furthermore, there is a protective stop in place if a collision happens so the worker will not be injured. However, this will cause the robot to stop which in turn stops the whole line and a restart will be needed. This means a loss in production. One way to solve this problem is to alert the human part that a collision will happen so that they can move out of the robot's way. Another way is to create a system that can detect obstacles and can recreate the path of the robotic arm in real time so that it avoids possible collisions. In this work, I will create a solution that contains both systems. An XR device will help the human worker by showing the robot's movement in advance. This way one can see where the machine intends to move in the next second and can move out of the way. This AR device will be responsible for scanning the worker's hands in real-time based on which collisions can be predicted. The robotic arm's path will be recreated by mathematically modeling the environment and fitting polynomials, parametric curves, and splines on it so that the most efficient route is found that avoids the obstacle. The expected result of my thesis is a technology that enables true collaboration between humans and robots by minimizing or even eliminating the risks.

Chapter 2

Previous work

This work is based on a project called PREHUROCO [1] on which I have worked for the past 2 years in SZTAKI. PREdictor for HUman-RObot COLLision (PREHUROCO) is a real-time collision detection system for collaborative robots, which alerts human workers about future collisions. At the time when PREHUROCO was first started, obstacle avoidance systems were already in the industry [2, 3], however with the new XR devices new options opened up. One of the new options on which PREHUROCO was built is that the human worker can be alerted of possible collisions by such a device. At that time the sufficiently capable XR device such as Hololens 2 has just started to appear. Therefore using the Hololens 2 device in an industry environment was a novelty. This project was made with ApertusVR and uses a Microsoft Kinect v2 and a smartwatch as well as an XR device that is Hololens 2.

- ApertusVR is the backbone with which the different parts are connected.
- The worker is detected by the Microsoft Kinect which creates a point cloud.
- The smartwatch gives haptic feedback about future collisions.
- The XR device gives visual feedback on the robot's movements.

Based on the point cloud of the human and the pre-known path of the robotic arm a future collision can be predicted with ApertusVR. By having a virtual robotic arm move in advance (for example 1 second) the system can confidently alarm the worker to move away to avoid a collision. Alerting the worker is done by vibrating the smartwatch and showing the future movement of the robotic arm, which is also

done through ApertusVR. PREHUROCO has been tested in a relevant industry environment thus reaching TRL 6 and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the XR4ALL project with grant agreement No 825545. This proves that the industry needs systems like this, and makes it a viable path to follow. Although this achievement the project has a few weaknesses:

- Too many separate parts are needed (Kinect v2, smartwatch, Hololens 2, a computer, and the robot).
- The Kinect v2 itself can be a problem because sometimes it detects the robotic arm as a human.
- No obstacle avoidance, which means that if the worker does not move out of the robot's way despite the alarms, a collision will happen and a restart will be necessary for the whole line.
- ApertusVR although being a very useful engine is designed for large systems with multiple computers and tools, therefore it is computationally heavier than we would necessarily need

Hololens 2 can detect collisions, and although it can only track the hands of a worker, based on that a sufficiently accurate human model can be built to replace the point cloud. The haptic feedback is not necessary if ample visual feedback is given. This removes the need for two components: the smartwatch and the Kinect.

My thesis is intended to be an extension of PREHUROCO, by adding automatic obstacle avoidance and moving the the alert and collision detection system onto the Hololens 2 device, thus solving all of the aforementioned problems. Since the start of PREHUROCO there have been projects focusing on combining robotics with XR [4, 5], however, they do not build on the capabilities of Hololens 2, instead use many other devices such as depth cameras and AI-based object detection. Furthermore, most of them do not focus on an assembly process where the collaboration between robots and humans is essential. My thesis aims to provide a whole solution to this problem using only the Hololens 2 device and the robotic arm.

2.0.1 The new system

My work consists of creating a new system that is only using the Hololens 2 and the robotic arm to avoid obstacles, there is no other device, camera, or computer needed. Although there are obstacle avoidance systems available, most of them do not utilize the new XR devices. The PREHUROCO project's main task was to utilize the XR technology for feedback about the movement of the robot, my main task was to take it further and create a system that is capable of giving visual feedback to workers like PREHUROCO, but if they cannot avoid a collision the system itself avoids it. The new system consists of 2 main parts:

- Robot control
- The virtual reality

To control the robot, the UR5's inverse kinematics had to be implemented. This was already done by others but it is not publicly available. However, there are techniques available that are used for general 6DoF manipulators based on which our own inverse kinematics can be written. The virtual reality consists of 3 main parts:

- Virtual robots (a robot for the present and the future movement)
- A human model based on data provided by Hololens 2
- Collision detection and avoidance system

The virtual robots were the main innovation in PREHUROCO, and I used them similarly, but thanks to obstacle avoidance, the new software is capable of showing the robot's future movement even if the path is rewritten. In PREHUROCO the prediction was static, and the predefined path could not be changed at runtime. On top of the movement prediction, there is a human model entirely based on the data provided by Hololens 2. There are devices and techniques used to simulate human movement, but they require separate cameras or entire body data. I created a human model that does not require anything else but the Hololens 2. In the object avoidance system, the new idea is that we only need to check in certain directions for new paths. Based on this the calculations can be done in 2D, and then reverse-projected into 3D, thus enabling much faster calculations.

Chapter 3

Work environment

In my thesis, I focus on a specific work environment (Figure 3.1), with some options for generalization. The aim is to have a complete solution for the following specifications: A robotic arm around waist height on a work table. The human worker stands at one of the sides of the table and has to assemble something in cooperation with the robot. This is the most common setup in an industry environment where cooperation is required.

Figure 3.1: Work environment table setup

3.1 The robotic arm

In my work, I use an UR5 robotic arm that can be seen in figure 3.2. It has the following specifications:

Working radius	850 mm
Payload	5 kg
Joint ranges	+/- 360°
Speed	180°/s
Degrees of freedom	6
Weight	18.4 kg

Table 3.1: UR5 specifications

Figure 3.2: UR5 robot arm from Universal Robots webpage

This arm is ideal to work with because it has adequate work capacity and a far enough reach to be able to perform a large variety of tasks, furthermore, it is quite common in both industry and research environments. As can be seen in table 3.1 it has 6 controllable joints (6 DOF¹), which will be very important for recalculating paths.

¹degrees of freedom

3.2 Hololens 2

As specified before the solution focuses on the Hololens 2 device, therefore we must know at least roughly how it works, what is it capable of, and its specifications. Hololens 2 is a mixed-reality tool, which means it combines real-world and virtual environments. It is a relatively new device, it was first purchasable in 2019, and I started working with it in early 2021. It runs on its own without any external device needed. It has see-through holographic lenses called waveguides and has eye-based rendering so the display is optimized for 3D eye position. The following sensors are listed on the Microsoft Hololens webpage:

- 4 visible light camera
- 2 IR cameras
- 1-MP time-of-flight depth sensor²
- accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer
- 1080p30 video

Thanks to these sensors it is capable of real-time two-handed fully articulated hand tracking[6], World-scale position tracking, and real-time environment mesh creation. Additionally, it has a built-in spatial audio and speech recognition system, that enables users to control the device with voice commands. These features make it very useful and convenient to work with, opening up many opportunities. The only drawback in terms of development is that it is a Universal Windows device, which means only Universal Windows apps run on it, this makes native C++ app development quite difficult. Fortunately, Unity made it feasible to build UWP (Universal Windows Platform) apps for Hololens 2, so the decision was made to move the original PREHUROCO app from pure C++ to Unity C#.

3.3 Virtual environment

The virtual environment is what the Hololens 2 device creates on top of the real one. Its origin is always the device's position at the moment when the application

²Measures distance based on the time it takes for an artificial light signal to take the round-trip between the camera and the environment

starts. Its z axis is the axis of sight, y points upwards, and x points left. Fortunately, the devices map the real environment continuously, so once we have synchronized with the virtual one it can keep track of it. This synchronization can be done in multiple ways. In the PREHUROCO project first, we started by manually moving via TCP messages the virtual robot where it should be at every startup, from arbitrary starting positions. However this is not ideal, it could take up to 5 minutes to set up the Hololens 2 this way. Therefore we switched to a fixed starting position. We have made a mount (Figure 3.3) for the Hololens 2, we have saved the position of the virtual robot, in this reference frame, and at application startup this is automatically applied. The previous manual setting is still in place, in case something changes in the setup.

For this project, we have changed the setup. We created a new reference point for the virtual environment, and every virtual object (except the human model) is its child. This reference point can be freely moved in run-time, with the Hololens 2's input system. This means that the user simply can grab the reference point and move it where it should be. In addition to this, the aforementioned TCP message system is still in place, if for some reason the new solution is not viable.

(a) Mount for Hololens 2

(b) Hololens 2 on mount

Figure 3.3: Hololens 2 mount setup

Chapter 4

Simulating human movement

In this chapter, we will go through how the new human model is created. Instead of separate devices like the Kinect v2, we use only the HoloLens 2. This is beneficial because most work environments do not have the space to install external devices and working with too many different devices can cause problems. As the HoloLens 2 is on the worker's head, the work environment does not have to be modified to use the system and it contains everything needed to build a human model.

4.1 HoloLens 2 data

The first task before we can detect collisions is to create the objects that can collide. In this case, a human model and a virtual twin of the robotic arm are needed. In the previous chapter, we went through the properties of the HoloLens 2 device, so we know that it can track human hand movements in real-time, and can provide a virtual twin for it. Unfortunately, that's not quite enough, because we assume that the robotic arm is at waist height the upper body can collide too. Apart from the data of the hands we only get one more information directly from the HoloLens 2, and that is the head's 3D data (position and orientation). Based on this an estimate can be created of the worker's upper body. One way to create a good model is to have an initialization step where the worker can set the essential values, another is to somehow scan the worker and fit a human avatar on this data (e.g. point cloud). For this project, it is necessary to have a very simple and fast initialization that can be done by anyone, therefore we chose the initialization step method, with a very simple setup. For a good estimate of the upper body, apart from the head, and hand

data, we need the length of the arms and the width of the shoulders. This we can get by instructing the worker to straighten his/her arms forward and have them be parallel. In this position, we can get the width of the shoulders by calculating the distance between the hands, and the length of the arms by calculating the distance between the hands and the head on the axis of sight (assuming the worker looks straight ahead).

Figure 4.1: Human model estimate

4.2 Estimations

We get the data of each hand separately by having the worker take the pose described before (and shown in Figure 4.1) and click first with the left then with the right hand. (On Hololens 2 clicking is done by touching the pointing finger and the thumb.) After this, the only information still needed is the size of the arms and the torso. However, for this, it will be enough to set values that are upper limits of each, because we do not want the robotic arm to be able to move close to the worker. Furthermore, the torso is almost unnecessary, because there is very little chance of a collision between the robot and the torso without the robot colliding with the hands or the head first. The reason for this is the setup (Figure 4.2), the robot being on a table means that the only way to have a human torso hit the robot is by moving the torso above the table.

Figure 4.2: Robot is set on a table at waist height

4.3 The arms

Each arm is represented by two cylinders. The upper arms are modeled with a diameter of 20 cm (assuming the largest arm size (perimeter) is 55 cm, with a 5 cm safe zone added). The forearms are similar but they have a smaller diameter, we use 16cm instead of 20cm. We must handle the bending of the arms, for this another continuous estimation is needed.

4.3.1 2D movement of the arms

We need a way to follow the entire arms movement as closely as possible based on the data provided by Hololens 2. Based on the position and orientation of the hand we use 2D 2 DOF inverse kinematics [7], with which we get a very good approximation of the angle at the elbow and at the shoulder. These are decreasing (the forearm and upper arm get closer) as the hand moves closer to the body. This can be seen in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Change in angles as the hand moves closer

We will calculate these angles in 2D, for this we have to define the 2D plane in which it is done (later we will extend it to 3D). At first, we start with the plane formed by the y and z axes. As can be seen in Figure 4.3 the hands move up-down on the y axis and move closer-farther to the body on the z axis. On this plane, we can calculate everything using triangle geometry. We can define a right triangle where one side is a line between the shoulder joint and the hand, one is straight down from the hand to the shoulder's height, and the last one is a parallel line to axis z from the shoulder to the hand Figure 4.4. To calculate γ we can use tangent¹:

$$\tan(\gamma) = \frac{b}{a}$$

$$\gamma = \text{atan2}(b, a)$$

4.3.

¹We use `atan2` instead of `atan` because it provides a solution in a wider range: $[-\pi, \pi]$

Figure 4.4: Right triangle on (z,y) plane

With this we can always point the model arm straight towards the hand, thus we can mimic straight arm movement. The next step is to calculate the angles inside the triangle formed by the hand, elbow, and shoulder.

Figure 4.5: Triangle formed by hand, elbow and shoulder

In Figure 4.5 l_1 is the length of the upper arm, l_2 is the length of the forearm, and d is the distance between the hand and the shoulder. The angle marked by blue is a right angle. We need to calculate β and α . From the law of cosines, we get:

$$\beta = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{l_1^2 + l_2^2 - d^2}{2l_1l_2} \right)$$

and by using the tangent as before we get:

$$\alpha = \text{atan2}(\ell_2 \sin(\pi - \beta), \ell_1 + \ell_2 \cos(\pi - \beta))$$

It is important to note that there are two possible values for β because the elbow can either point up or down. Since we know that it is a human model, we always choose the angle pointing down. Furthermore, β is not the angle with which the arm is rotated, but its supplementary angle, however considering:

$$\cos(\beta) = -\cos(\pi - \beta)$$

We can simply multiply the fraction in *arccos* by -1 to get the correct angle and replace β with it. The last step is to apply these angles, α is the angle between the line from the shoulder to the hand and the line where the upper arm should be. To achieve this position we need to subtract α from γ and rotate the upper arm that much. In conclusion, the upper arm has to be rotated $\gamma - \alpha$ degrees and the forearm has to be rotated β degrees to accurately model the arm's movements on the (z, y) plane.

4.3.2 Extending the arm model into 3D

To move from 2D to 3D the first step is to handle movement on the 3rd axis (x). This is easily solved by the previously used tangent method. Applying it to the triangle defined by the shoulder, elbow, and hand triplet based on the (x, z) plane. Unfortunately, this only solves the movement on the (x, z) plane, if the hand moves up or down, it does not provide an accurate solution. To combine the solution for the (z, y) and (x, z) planes, we have to define an order between them, solve the first one, and based on that solution solve the second one. This can work if after one of them has been solved we do not solve the other one on its original plane but in a new reference frame defined by the new positions.

Figure 4.6: Changing coordinate systems for calculation

Changing planes (or shifting coordinate systems) enables us to use the same calculations as before if the new coordinate system is the shoulder's local system. However, this only uses the position of the hands, we need to handle the orientation separately. If we examine how our arms move as the hand rotates (based on Figure 4.7) we can see that we can rotate our hand on the z and x axes without moving our arms, but as we rotate around the y axis our elbow moves. More precisely if we rotate our hand counter-clockwise our elbow moves to the right, otherwise to the left. With further examination, it can be seen that the movement of the elbow is caused by the rotation of the shoulder joint on its z axis, and the angle is approximately the same as the hand rotates on the y axis.

Figure 4.7: Changing coordinate systems for calculation

If we apply this rotation on the shoulder before our calculations and shift our coordinate system accordingly, we can use the geometric method described before

to get a complete model of the arm's movement, that is accurate enough for our collision tests. In Unity, this can be done by first using the aforementioned tangent method to point the shoulder towards the hand (the shoulder's z axis). This moves the shoulder's coordinate system to the right place. To calculate everything on this plane we need to know the position of the hand on this plane, which can be calculated by using the inverse of the shoulder's transformation matrix:

$$H' = S^{-1} \cdot H$$

H is the hand's, S is the shoulder's transformation matrix, and H' is the hand's transformation matrix in the shoulder's reference frame. With this, we simplified the calculation because by pointing the shoulder's z axis toward the hand, we ensured that in the shoulder's coordinate system, the hand's position will always be $(x, y, z) = (0, 0, d)$, where d is the distance of the hand from the shoulder. In the final software, this human model will not be visible, because it greatly blocks the view of the worker. The model will be in the background, purely used for collision detection.

Figure 4.8: Left hand with model on top of it, right without model

4.3.3 Arm movement based on ragdoll effect

Another way to move the arms based on the hand's movements is to use some type of ragdoll effect [8]. This effect was first used in computer games to enable characters to have more realistic movements. Basically, they switched from predefined animations, to physics-based skeleton movement. Fortunately, we only want to

handle a skeleton built up from 2 bones. If we attach the forearm to the wrist of the hand model, the forearm will follow every movement of the hand as accurately (or in some cases even more accurately) as our triangle geometry-based algorithm. If we further attach the upper arm to the end of the forearm, where the elbow is, and attach the end of the upper arm to the shoulder, we create a chain that is controlled by the hand the the shoulder. This setup can be in most cases more accurate than the previously described method while being much more simple. However, in cases where the hands take up very unusual positions (in terms of assembly), it can even "break apart" the model. For example when our hand points straight up and our palm points forward:

Figure 4.9: Unusual hand pose

We previously mentioned what causes the problem: the wrist can rotate some degrees without the arm moving. We could build in some threshold under which the forearm does not move, but that would cause it to lag behind that amount always, so it is better to have it break sometimes. In the final software, the user can choose between the two models anytime by pressing a button.

4.4 Movement prediction

The aim is to foresee possible future collisions, for this it is not enough to know the movement of the robot and the worker in the present, we must project them forward into the future. In the case of the robot, as we know the exact path it follows, it is very easy to calculate where it will be in any second. However, the worker's movements are considerably harder to anticipate. Workers can change directions, slow down, or speed up at any moment in an instant. Thus we cannot hope for a

predictor that is always very accurate. On the other hand, we only need to predict human movement in the near future (0.1-0.2 sec in advance), because we can exactly predict the robot's position, and the aim is to have the robotic arm avoid obstacles that are in the way. We also simplify the hands, because we do not need as detailed models as the Hololens 2 creates, for the simulation we represent them as cuboids. This also provides a very simple way to create a safe zone around the hand that the robot cannot enter, by increasing this shape to such a size that it contains the desired safe zone around the hand too. Hololens 2 also predicts movements, to try to follow the real-time movement, as it is constantly behind the real world with at least one frame (16.67 ms). However, this prediction is not good enough to follow the hands. In all tests even moderate speeds, caused the model to be around 0.1 seconds late. The reason for this is that they wanted to avoid predicting the model to be in the wrong place, so they chose to make it a little late but very accurate. In our case the opposite is needed, as we aim for safety, it is better to have some false positive predictions, in advance than true positives a little late. It is necessary to know where the worker's hands can be, thus we need to compensate for the lateness of the Hololens 2 with a prediction. As the hands are physical objects, we know that they follow certain rules. They must always have continuous acceleration (and deceleration), which means that the second derivatives of the positions are continuous, thus the first derivatives and the positions are also continuous. Based on this, we can set up an algorithm that calculates both the first and the second derivatives from the positions. We get the first derivative's estimation by subtracting the last position from the current one. We get the estimation of the second derivative by calculating the previous first derivative and subtracting it from the current one. We assume that the data is equidistant. Assuming this distance is h , and the current time is t , $x[t]$ is the previous, and $x[t + h]$ is the current position. Then the finite differences (in this case forward difference) can be calculated:

$$\Delta x[t] = \frac{x[t + h] - x[t]}{h}$$

and the second order (central) difference is:

$$\Delta^2 x[t] = \frac{x[t + h] - 2x[t] + x[t - h]}{h^2}.$$

We know that if a real function is differentiable at a point, we can approximate it linearly, for this we use the Taylor series. Substituting the above-mentioned into the Taylor series we can calculate a prediction for any t time:

$$x[a] = x[t] + \Delta x[t](a - t) + \frac{\Delta^2 x[t](a - t)^2}{2}$$

Where $a > t$ is a future time at when we would like to know the position. If we want to predict for one h step forward, we get the following, assuming we are at $t + h$:

$$x[t + 2h] = x[t + h] + \Delta x[t + h]h + \frac{\Delta^2 x[t + h]h^2}{2}$$

The series can go on forever with each further member added the approximation getting more accurate, however assuming very small steps, we get a small error even with just the second derivatives:

$$|\epsilon| \leq \frac{\Delta^3 x}{6} h^3$$

At first, we used the smallest possible stepsize 0.0167 s, which means that we took the position at every frame, however, the tests did not yield sufficiently accurate results. Even for small predictions (0.1 sec), it can be off by large values. The cause of this is the small fluctuations in the position the Hololens 2 provides. Even if one does not move, the data provided by the device can move around by approximately 0.1 cm. This will be detected by the system as movement, thus it predicts the hand to move even further in the same direction, resulting in a greater error. Therefore we modified the data, we still take the position at every frame, but we take the average of 3 data points to form one, thus we apply a sort of integral filter, which is known to decrease noise. Using this method the stepsize is greater it is around 0.05s but we significantly decreased to amount of fluctuation between two data points. With this final addition, the prediction of hand movement is sufficiently accurate to use in real-time obstacle detection. Furthermore, we have achieved a better model than the previously used point cloud provided by the Kinect v2 in PREHUROCO, therefore eliminating the need for an additional tool.

Chapter 5

Robot control

In this chapter, we will go through the forward and inverse kinematics of the UR5 robotic arm. As mentioned before solutions exist for 6 DoF arms, but specifically for the UR5 arm it is not publicly available. Although SZTAKI provided a DLL containing a well-optimized solution that we use in the software, we will implement our own, so that in the future we can create new techniques with it for obstacle avoidance. It is also beneficial to understand how the algorithm works, it enables us to create a better avoidance system.

5.1 Predefined path

There is always a predefined path that the robotic arm has to follow as far as possible. We assume that this path is given, and we can read it, and if necessary modify it on the fly. On this path, we must have synchronization points where we can check that the virtual twin is where it should be, and if not, we correct the position. This is unavoidable because the real robotic arm's speed can fluctuate between runs because of environmental factors. These synchronization points can be predefined too, but in case they are missing, they can be created when the path is loaded. They do not have to be equidistant, but if they are not predefined, we put one at every 3 seconds. These are very important because when we recalculate the path to avoid an obstacle, we only calculate between the current position and the closest reachable synchronization point. This saves computational time and (assuming the predefined path is the most efficient in terms of collaboration) decreases assembling time, and makes the robot more predictable, which increases safety. Furthermore, a

synchronization point has to be at every critical time. A critical time is when the robot has to pick something up or put something down. These points are special in the sense that it is not allowed for the robot to miss them. If for some reason a path cannot be created on which the obstacle is avoided but the critical point is reached the robot must stop, and wait for the path to get clear. These paths are created so that humans can easily work with the robotic arm, therefore there is always room for error. If in the next step, the worker has to assemble something, the robotic arm either does something else or waits in the meantime. In the case of obstacle avoidance, this downtime is perfect, because it gives a chance to move on a longer path that steers clear of obstacles without increasing the total assembling time.

5.2 Kinematics

We want to control the robot's movements, thus we need to solve the inverse kinematics of the UR5. Before we can do this we have to go through the description of the robot's pose in space and the solution of its forward kinematics with which we can calculate the gripper's position from the joint angles. First of all, we need to know the kinematics of the robotic arm to be able to describe its motion in space. The robot's pose can be defined either in joint space by 6 joint angles or in position space by the coordinates of the gripper. Additionally, we will use each joint's transformation matrix that contains both of the aforementioned information. In joint space, we have to define the rotational angle of each joint, therefore we need a vector with 6 dimensions:

$$R_j = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \\ \theta_4 \\ \theta_5 \\ \theta_6 \end{bmatrix}$$

θ_i is the rotational angle in radians of the i th joint around its z axis. In position space, we need a $3D$ vector to describe the coordinates of the gripper:

$$P_g = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix}$$

We need a mapping between the two. As mentioned before with forward kinematics we can calculate the position from the joint angles, hence we will have a function:

$$forward : [-\pi, \pi]^6 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$$

We know that for: $R_j = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T$:

$$forward(R_j) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}^T$$

Unfortunately, in the case of inverse kinematics, we will have multiple solutions thus we can only define a relation:

$$inverse : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow [-\pi, \pi]^6$$

where for each $P_g = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \end{bmatrix}^T \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $inverse(P_g)$ will be a subset of $[-\pi, \pi]^6$. On the other hand, the multiple solutions will give us one more option to avoid obstacles by simply choosing the one that does not collide with it, (if that exists). This is a very good solution for stationary obstacles (or for very slow-moving ones).

5.2.1 Forward kinematics

We first begin with the frame assignment to get the Denavit Hartenberg parameters [9]. These parameters (also called DH parameters) are 4 values attached to each joint to describe their movement. We chose each joint's reference frame by following these steps:

1. the axis around which the joint rotates will be the z axis,
2. for the first joint the x axis is arbitrary (perpendicular to z), for the other joints x will be parallel to the common normal of the current joint's and the previous joint's z axis pointing away from the previous z ,
3. the y axis will be the one that completes the right-handed reference frame

The DH parameters are:

- d : distance from origin to common normal (in case the previous and current z are parallel d is a free parameter)
- θ : angle around the previous z axis between the previous and the current x

- r : length of the common normal
- α : angle around the current x between the previous and the current z

Fortunately, the DH parameters are available on the Universal Robots webpage for almost every one of their robots along with Figure 5.1 on which the previously described frame assignment along with the DH parameters can be seen.

Figure 5.1: UR5 frame assignment

We get the following table of DH parameters from Universal Robots webpage:

Joints	θ	r	d	α
1	0	0	0.089159	$\frac{\pi}{2}$
2	0	-0.425	0	0
3	0	-0.3922	0	0
4	0	0	0.10915	$\frac{\pi}{2}$
5	0	0	0.09465	$-\frac{\pi}{2}$
6	0	0	0.0823	0

With the DH parameters, we can get the transformation matrix between the reference frames. From the $i - 1$ th to the i th the matrix takes the following form:

$${}_{i-1}T_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_i & -\sin \theta_i \cos \alpha_i & \sin \theta_i \sin \alpha_i & r_i \cos \theta_i \\ \sin \theta_i & \cos \theta_i \cos \alpha_i & -\cos \theta_i \sin \alpha_i & r_i \sin \theta_i \\ 0 & \sin \alpha_i & \cos \alpha_i & d_i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

Further on we will denote the transformation from the k -th reference frame to the ℓ -th by ${}^kT_\ell$, $\cos \theta_k$ by c_k , $\sin \theta_k$ by s_k , $\cos(\theta_k + \theta_\ell)$ by $c_{k\ell}$ and $\sin \theta_k + \theta_\ell$ by $s_{k\ell}$. By substituting the DH parameters into Table 5.1 we get the following transformation

matrices:

$$\begin{aligned}
 {}^0_1T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & 0 & s_1 & 0 \\ s_1 & 0 & c_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.089159 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & {}^1_2T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_2 & -s_2 & 0 & -0.425c_2 \\ s_2 & c_2 & 0 & -0.425s_2 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
 {}^2_3T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_3 & -s_3 & 0 & -0.3922c_3 \\ s_3 & c_3 & 0 & -0.3922s_3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & {}^3_4T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_4 & 0 & s_4 & 0 \\ s_4 & 0 & -c_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.10915 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\
 {}^4_5T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_5 & 0 & -s_5 & 0 \\ s_5 & 0 & c_5 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0.09465 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, & {}^5_6T &= \begin{bmatrix} c_6 & -s_6 & 0 & 0 \\ s_6 & c_6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0.0823 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

We can get all the other transformation matrices by simply multiplying these, for example, to get the gripper's transformation matrix we need to multiply all of them in the correct order:

$${}^0_6T = {}^0_1T {}^1_2T {}^2_3T {}^3_4T {}^4_5T {}^5_6T$$

This contains the orientation and position of the gripper:

$${}^0_6T = \begin{bmatrix} & & p_x \\ & {}^0_6R & p_y \\ & & p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

0_6R is the rotation matrix, (p_x, p_y, p_z) is the position of the gripper. We get the following values for the position:

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_x &= 0.09465(c_{23}c_1s_1 + s_{23}c_1c_4) + 0.3922(c_1s_2s_3 - c_1c_2c_3) \\
 &\quad + 0.0823(c_5s_1 - c_{234}c_1s_5) - 0.425c_1c_2 + 0.10915s_1 \quad (5.2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_y &= 0.09465(c_{23}s_1s_4 + s_{23}c_4s_1) + 0.3922(s_1s_2s_3 - s_1c_2c_3) \\
 &\quad - 0.0823(c_1c_5 - c_{234}s_1s_5) - 0.425c_2s_2 - 0.10915c_1 \quad (5.3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 p_z &= 0.09465(s_{23}s_4 + c_{23}c_4) - 0.3922s_{23} \\
 &\quad - 0.0823s_5(c_{23}s_4 - s_{23}c_4) - 0.425s_2 + 0.165 \quad (5.4)
 \end{aligned}$$

All of the positions only contain θ -s as a parameter, therefore we have our forward

kinematics function. We can plug in any joint angle set into them and get the coordinates of the gripper.

5.2.2 Inverse kinematics

The robot's computer contains an inverse kinematics calculation, with which we can move the robot wherever we want, however, we cannot use that on the Hololens 2 device. Furthermore, we would like to have free control of the robotic arm at any time, which includes the choice of one of the multiple solutions to the inverse kinematics calculation [10, 11].

Similarly to forward kinematics we will use the ${}^k_\ell T$ transformation matrices, just backward. We start from:

$${}^0_6T = \begin{bmatrix} & & p_x \\ & {}^0_6R & p_y \\ & & p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Which will now contain the desired orientation and position instead of the current. This means that we know every value in this matrix, and we would like to calculate θ_i for $i \in [1, 6]$ using it. Usually for 6 DoF robots the task can be separated into two subtasks, one is to calculate the wrist rotation (the wrist is the last 3 joints) and the other is to calculate the first 3 joint orientations based on that. Unfortunately, this can only be done if the robot's wrist is spherical (the last 3 joints intersect at the same point) and the UR5's wrist is not spherical.

We will start with calculating θ_1 . For this first, we will need the position of the 5th reference frame denoted by 0_5P . Since we know the position of the gripper which is the 6th reference frame we know that by going backward on its z axis by d_6 (which is equivalent to the distance between the 2 joints) we get the position of the 5th joint. Thus we get:

$${}^0_5P = {}^0_6T \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -d_6 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now if we examine Figure 5.3 we can see that the origins of the first 4 joints are all on the same plane that is spanned by z_0 and x_1 . Furthermore, we can see that the 5th reference frame is at d_4 distance from this plane. Now if we were to rotate joints 2,3,4 and 5 respectively around z_1 , z_2 , z_3 , and z_4 , this distance would stay the

d_4 , which means that these rotations only move the 5th joint on the plane that is parallel to the one spanned by z_0 and x_1 shifted by d_4 .

Figure 5.2: Reference frames of the joints

This consequently means that the 5th joint can only move on the y_0 axis on the plane spanned by y_0, x_0 if the base rotates. Therefore since we know the desired position, we can calculate the angle to point the base towards there, by projecting this position on the aforementioned plane, by calculating the angle between x_0 and the projected point. Fortunately, the previously calculated 0_5P contains the value of this point since it is the 5th joint's position in the base's reference frame:

$$\gamma = \text{atan2} \left({}^0_5P_y, {}^0_5P_x \right)$$

This will point x_0 straight toward the desired position, however, as we can see in Figure 5.3 it is not exactly correct, that is because of the d_4 shift mentioned earlier. To get the correct value, we need to offset it by the angle with which z_1 would have to be rotated to point towards the desired point:

$$\delta = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{d_4}{\sqrt{{}^0_5P_x^2 + {}^0_5P_y^2}} \right)$$

This angle would point z_1 towards the right direction, however, we need to point x_0 , which is parallel to x_1 which has a 90 deg rotation compared to z_1 . In conclusion,

we have two values as solutions:

$$\theta_1 = \gamma + \text{delta} + \frac{\pi}{2}$$

We have two solutions because the arm can be to the right or to the left of the desired position since it can rotate its end effector around. If we examine the solution we can derive that we will have a solution if $d_4 \leq \sqrt{{}^0P_x^2 + {}^0P_y^2}$. Otherwise, the distance to the desired position would be shorter than d_4 which can be viewed as the length from the middle line of the robot to the 5th joint or the wrist of the robot, this means it cannot enter this area. The workspace is defined in the UR5-s manual too, where we can see, this unreachable area:

Figure 5.3: Unreachable area from UR5 manual

We continue by calculating θ_5 . If we examine the transformation matrices focusing on θ_5 , we can find that ${}^1_6T[3, 4] = 0.09465c_5 + 0.10915$, where

$${}^1_6T = {}^1_2T {}^2_3T {}^3_4T {}^4_5T {}^5_6T$$

On the other side:

$${}^1_6T = ({}^0_1T)^{-1} {}^0_6T$$

$${}^1_6T = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & s_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.089159 \\ s_1 & -c_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} {}^0_6R & p_x \\ p_y \\ p_z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore we can get ${}^1_6T[3, 4]$ by multiplying the 3rd row of $({}^0_1T)^{-1}$ with the 4th column of 0_6T . (Here we should remember that 0_6T contains the desired position and orientation, hence we know every value in it). From the multiplication we get

${}^1_6T[3, 4] = s_1p_x - c_1p_y$, thus we can write the equation:

$$0.09465 \cos(\theta_5) + 0.10915 = \sin(\theta_1)p_x - \cos(\theta_1)p_y$$

Since we have already calculated θ_1 , we can solve for θ_5 :

$$\theta_5 = \pm \arccos\left(\frac{\sin(\theta_1)p_x - \cos(\theta_1)p_y - 0.10915}{0.09465}\right)$$

Here we have two solutions again because the wrist can point either downwards or upwards in the same position. Next, we will calculate θ_6 , and we use 1_6T once again.

On the one hand, we have that for ${}^1_6T = {}^1_2T {}^2_3T {}^3_4T {}^4_5T {}^5_6T$:

$${}^1_6T = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ c_6s_5 & -s_5s_6 & c_5 & p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

on the other hand for ${}^1_6T = ({}^0_1T)^{-1} {}^0_6T$ we have:

$${}^1_6T = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & s_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -0.089159 \\ s_1 & -c_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} & p_x \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} & p_y \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} & p_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

From this we can derive the following equality:

$$\begin{bmatrix} c_6s_5 \\ -s_5s_6 \\ c_5 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11}s_1 - r_{21}c_1 \\ r_{12}s_1 - r_{22}c_1 \\ r_{13}s_1 - r_{23}c_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

In the above, we know every value except for θ_6 , so we can solve it:

$$\theta_6 = \text{atan2}\left(\frac{r_{22} \cos(\theta_1) - r_{12} \sin(\theta_1)}{\sin(\theta_5)}, \frac{r_{11} \sin(\theta_1) - r_{21} \cos(\theta_1)}{\sin(\theta_5)}\right)$$

We can see that if $\sin(\theta_5) = 0$ then θ_6 is not well defined. This happens when joints 2,3,4 and 6 are parallel causing the system to have infinite solutions. This however can be solved by predefining a value for θ_6 for this case. We are left with θ_2, θ_3 and θ_4 . We can see in Figure 5.5 that all of these joints are on the same plane. Furthermore, if we rotate around z_1, z_2 , and z_3 they will stay on that plane. Thus if we assume for a moment that the transformation matrices of Joint 0 and 5 are fixed, we can

view these last three joints as a separate robot with 3 joints, which has its base at Joint 0 and its desired position at Joint 5. Since we know the transformation matrix of the base and we can calculate back from the desired 0_6T to get the position and orientation of Joint 5 (we know θ_5 and θ_6) we can work out the last 3 angles by calculating on the aforementioned plane.

Figure 5.4: Last 3 joints are on the same plane

With the previous description, we get a planar 3R manipulator, for which the solution is very similar to the one we used for the arms in the human model in Section 4.3.1. We start by θ_2 and θ_3 . Following the same logic as in the case of the arms we can draw the following triangle:

Figure 5.5: Geometry of θ_2 and θ_3

Where x and y are Joint 4's position in the reference frame of Joint 1:

$${}^1_3T = \begin{bmatrix} & & x \\ & {}^1_3R & y \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

To get this position we can work backward since we know everything in the last two transformation matrices:

$${}^1_4T = {}^1_6T({}_6^4T)^{-1}$$

Since we do not need the full 1_3T matrix, only the position (the last column), and we know that we can get the position of the 5th joint by shifting the 4th joint on its z axis by d_4 (Figure 5.1). Therefore by shifting the 5th joint on its y axis by $-d_4$ we can get the position we need:

$${}^1_3P = {}^1_4T \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -d_4 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now we can calculate β using the law of cosines:

$$\beta = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2} - a_2^2 - a_3^2}{2a_2a_3} \right)$$

Similarly to the arms, we need the supplementary angle of β to get θ_3 :

$$\theta_3 = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{a_2^2 + a_3^2 - \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{2a_2a_3} \right)$$

Here have have two values for θ_3 which correspond to the shoulder being up or down like the human models elbow could be up or down. To Point Joint 2 straight toward Joint 4 we can calculate the angle like before:

$$\gamma = \text{atan2}(y, x)$$

Applying the law of sines yields:

$$\alpha = \arcsin \left(\frac{a_3 \sin(\beta)}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}} \right)$$

$$\theta_2 = -(\gamma + \alpha)$$

Finally, only θ_4 is left. We will use the transformation matrices once again. On the one hand, we have:

$${}^3_4T = \begin{bmatrix} c_4 & 0 & s_4 & 0 \\ s_4 & 0 & -c_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0.10915 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

On the other hand with ${}^1_4T = {}^1_6T({}^4_6T)^{-1}$ and ${}^3_4T = ({}^1_3T)^{-1}{}^1_4T$ we have:

$${}^3_4T = \begin{bmatrix} -c_{23}(r_{13}s_5 - r_{11}c_5c_6 + r_{12}c_5s_6) - s_{23}(r_{23}s_5 - r_{21}c_5c_6 + r_{22}c_5s_6) & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ -s_{23}(r_{13}s_5 - r_{11}c_5c_6 + r_{12}c_5s_6) - c_{23}(r_{23}s_5 - r_{21}c_5c_6 + r_{22}c_5s_6) & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Since we know every value in the second form of 3_4T we can calculate θ_4 using the first and second element of the first column of both matrices:

$$\theta_4 = \text{atan2}({}^3_4T[1, 2], {}^3_4T[1, 1])$$

In conclusion, we have two possible values for θ_1 , θ_3 , and θ_5 therefore we can expect 8 possible configurations of joints for each position. Of course, it can happen that not all 8 are viable if the conditions are not met (e.g. the parameter of *arccos* is greater than 1), in that case, we will have fewer options. To choose one is up to us. Generally, we will choose a configuration where the shoulder is up and the robot "looks down" like in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6: Robotic arm "looking down"

In the final software, the inverse kinematics calculation is not done in Unity

C#, but with a DLL written in C++ provided by SZTAKI. This change was made because the DLL provided by SZTAKI is well-optimized, and the inverse kinematics calculations will be the backbone of the software which will have to be carried out multiple times when an obstacle is detected, thus it has to be as fast as possible. On the other hand for testing purposes and for possible other solutions that use the transformation matrix values as parameters it is good to have inverse kinematics solved.

Chapter 6

Obstacle avoidance

In this chapter, we go through everything needed for obstacle avoidance. We would like a system that if a collision is predicted and an obstacle has been detected can recalculate the robotic arm's path so that it goes around the obstacle and return to a synchronization point as soon as possible. Instead of a 3D map around the obstacle, we only use data from 3 predefined directions, thus the computation can be much faster. The way we solve this is by assuming we know the position and rough shape of the obstacle, we define points along the shape of the object and fit a parametric curve (in our case a spline) on it. We do not necessarily need cubic splines for moving the robotic arm, a linear interpolation (spline of degree 1) would be sufficient, because when we move the robot along the spline, we split it into n points and go from point to point. However, in the future, we would like to use this system to control vehicles (cars, drones) to enable them to avoid obstacles too. Another reason for splines is that we would like to be able to avoid moving objects, and the spline's parameters give us a way to calculate paths around moving objects quickly.

6.1 Parametric curves

The general form of parametric curves is the following:

$$\Theta : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2/\mathbb{R}^3, I \subset \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{R}^2$$

For $t \in I$

$$\Theta(t) = (\Theta_1(t), \Theta_2(t))$$

This gives a very intuitive description of paths and surfaces, which is the cause that it is commonly used in 3D applications. For kinematics we can define a curve that has time t as a parameter: $(x(t), y(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ or $(x(t), y(t), z(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^3$. If we record an object's position at every $t \in [0, T]$ time, we get a parametric curve that describes the object's motion in space. Assuming it is a real object's data, we know that it is continuously differentiable. By calculating the derivative at any t point we get the velocity of the object at that time. Fortunately calculating the derivative of a parametric curve is simple:

$$\Theta'(t) = (\Theta'_1(t), \Theta'_2(t))$$

Therefore we can calculate the derivative by differentiating the parts separately. Of course, the result is the velocity in each direction, to get the total velocity we need the length of the result:

$$v(t) = |\Theta'(t)| = \sqrt{\Theta'_1(t)^2 + \Theta'_2(t)^2}$$

Similarly, we can calculate the acceleration by calculating the second derivative:

$$a(t) = v'(t) = |\Theta''(t)|$$

Additionally, it can describe shapes in a very useful way. It enables us to iterate through each point of the sphere by simply calculating Θ at every point in I . For example a sphere with the center at $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and radius $r \in \mathbb{R}$ is:

$$\Theta(\theta, \phi) = (x_1 + r \cos \theta \sin \phi, x_2 + r \sin \theta \sin \phi, x_3 + r \cos \phi)$$

Where $\theta \in [0, 2\Pi]$ and $\phi \in [0, \Pi]$. The properties mentioned above are the reason we use them for object avoidance. If possible in all cases we would like to have the robot follow a smooth path around an obstacle.

6.1.1 Splines

Splines are piece-wise parametric polynomials [12], where the parameters are usually associated with the shape of the curve. The definition of k degree spline on $[a, b]$ is:

$$S : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

is a spline if:

- $S \in C^{k-1}[a, b]$
- $S(x) = \begin{cases} S_0(x), & x_0 \leq x \leq x_1 \\ S_1(x), & x_1 \leq x \leq x_2 \\ \vdots \\ S_{n-1}(x), & x_{n-1} \leq x \leq x_n \end{cases}$, where $a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_n = b$
- $S_i \in \mathcal{P}^k$

We will use piece-wise cubic spline interpolations to compute possible paths around an obstacle. Cubic splines (with the previous definition) are splines of degree $k = 3$, where:

$$S_i(x) = a_i + b_i(x - x_i) + c_i(x - x_i)^2 + d_i(x - x_i)^3, \quad x_i \leq x \leq x_{i+1} \quad (6.1)$$

The task is to find the coefficients a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i that fit our data. In the following, we will go through briefly how the coefficients of the cubic splines can be calculated. Suppose that our data follows a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. We must go through each data point, which means that:

$$S(x_i) = y_i \quad \text{if} \quad f(x_i) = y_i.$$

Substituting x_i into (6.1) we get:

$$S(x_i) = a_i \quad \implies \quad a_i = y_i$$

We know that $S \in C^2$, so we go further by taking the first and second derivatives:

$$S'_i(x) = b_i + 2c_i(x - x_i) + 3d_i(x - x_i)^2$$

$$S''_i(x) = 2c_i + 6d_i(x - x_i)$$

Substituting x_i into them gives $S'_i(x_i) = b_i$ and $S''_i(x_i) = 2c_i$. Furthermore, cubic spline interpolation requires a smooth transition between the pieces, which manifests in the following conditions:

$$S_i(x_{i+1}) = S_{i+1}(x_{i+1}) = a_{i+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S'_i(x_{i+1}) &= S'_{i+1}(x_{i+1}) = b_{i+1} \\ S''_i(x_{i+1}) &= S''_{i+1}(x_{i+1}) = 2c_{i+1} \end{aligned}$$

From now we assume equidistant data points (as we can get the obstacle's data in any desired step size):

$$h = x_1 - x_0 = x_2 - x_1 = \cdots = x_n - x_{n-1}$$

We can rewrite the previous equations using h :

$$\begin{aligned} S_i(x) &= a_i + b_i h + c_i h^2 + d_i h^3 = a_{i+1} \\ S'_i(x) &= b_i + 2c_i h + 3d_i h^2 = b_{i+1} \\ S''_i(x) &= 2c_i + 6d_i h = c_{i+1} \end{aligned}$$

From the above, we get the following:

$$d_i = \frac{c_{i+1} - c_i}{3h} \quad (6.2)$$

After some rearrangement and substituting (6.2) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{i+1} - a_i &= b_i h + \frac{c_{i+1} + 2c_i}{3} h^2 \\ b_{i+1} - b_i &= (c_{i+1} + c_i) h \end{aligned} \quad (6.3)$$

From the above, we can express b_i :

$$b_i = \frac{a_{i+1} - a_i}{h} - \frac{c_{i+1} + 2c_i}{3} h \quad (6.4)$$

By substituting this into (6.3) we get an equation only containing coefficients a_i and c_i (after rearranging, and moving the index down once):

$$c_{i-1} + 4c_i + c_{i+1} = 3 \frac{a_{i-1} - 2a_i + a_{i+1}}{h^2} \quad (6.5)$$

We already know the values of a_i (the real data values), hence we have a system of linear equations for c_i . Assuming we have $n + 1$ data points $[x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n]$, means we have n polynomials $[S_0(x), S_1(x), \dots, S_{n-1}]$ in the spline and n of each coefficient that we need. Therefore for each $1 \leq i \leq n - 2$ (6.5) can be written down. This

results in $n - 2$ equations for n number of c_i coefficients. To calculate n unknowns we need n equations, so we go further by setting boundary conditions. There are a number of conditions we can choose from, and based on this we get different splines. We will choose the commonly used natural condition to get a natural cubic spline. This condition simply sets $c_0 = c_n = 0$ or equivalently $S''(x_0) = S''(x_n) = 0$. This condition is known to provide a smooth curve without oscillations at the ends. We could use a clamped cubic spline, which requires us to know the derivatives at the endpoints of the data and set $S'(x_0)$ and $S'(x_n)$ according to that. Since we do know what the exact derivatives are, we can only numerically approximate them, this type could result in a worse approximation of the shape because we would approximate with approximated data. If we look at (6.5) we can see that it can be written in matrix form $Ac = B$, and not only matrix form but it is a tridiagonal system. With natural conditions, we have the following:

$$Ac = B$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & & & & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 1 & & & \\ & 1 & 4 & 1 & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & 1 & 4 & 1 \\ 0 & & & & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad c = \begin{bmatrix} c_0 \\ c_1 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3 \frac{a_0 - 2a_1 + a_2}{h^2} \\ 3 \frac{a_1 - 2a_2 + a_3}{h^2} \\ \vdots \\ 3 \frac{a_{n-1} - 2a_n + a_{n+1}}{h^2} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

On the other hand with a clamped cubic spline it would be:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & & & & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 1 & & & \\ & 1 & 4 & 1 & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & 1 & 4 & 1 \\ 0 & & & & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad c = \begin{bmatrix} c_0 \\ c_1 \\ \vdots \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 3 \frac{a_1 - a_0}{h^2} - 3 \frac{f'(x_0)}{h} \\ 3 \frac{a_0 - 2a_1 + a_2}{h^2} \\ 3 \frac{a_1 - 2a_2 + a_3}{h^2} \\ \vdots \\ 3 \frac{a_{n-1} - 2a_n + a_{n+1}}{h^2} \\ 3 \frac{f'(x_n)}{h} - 3 \frac{a_n - a_{n-1}}{h^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Both systems can be solved in $\mathcal{O}(n)$ time because A is tridiagonal, which is very good considering it will have to be solved many times on the Hololens 2 device, while it handles everything else from displaying the XR scene to calculating the human model described previously.

We use the Thomas algorithm to solve the system. It consists of 3 steps:

1. LU decomposition of A: $A = LU$
2. Calculating y with forward elimination, where $Ac = LUC = Ly = B$

3. Calculating c with backward elimination from $Uc = y$

LU decomposition

We would like to decompose A into a lower and an upper triangle matrix of the following form:

$$A = LU$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_0 & b_0 & & & 0 \\ c_0 & a_1 & b_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & c_{n-2} & a_{n-1} & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & & & c_{n-1} & a_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & & & & 0 \\ \ell_0 & 1 & & & \\ & \dots & \ddots & & \\ & & \ell_{n-2} & 1 & \\ 0 & & & \ell_{n-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_0 & b_0 & & & 0 \\ & u_1 & b_1 & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & u_{n-1} & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & & & & u_n \end{bmatrix}$$

The general algorithm is to calculate every ℓ_i and then every u_i . Of course, it can be done in the same cycle:

```

u0 = a0
for i = 1..n - 1 do
    ℓi = ci / ui
    ui+1 = ai+1 - ℓi · bi
end for

```

In our case, the matrices look like this:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & & & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 1 & & \\ & 1 & 4 & 1 & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots \\ & & & 1 & 4 & 1 \\ 0 & & & & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & & & & 0 \\ \ell_0 & 1 & & & \\ & \ell_1 & 1 & & \\ & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & \ell_{n-2} & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & & & \ell_{n-1} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_0 & 0 & & & 0 \\ & u_1 & 1 & & \\ & & u_2 & 1 & \\ & & & \ddots & \ddots \\ & & & & u_{n-1} & 1 \\ 0 & & & & 0 & u_n \end{bmatrix}$$

Therefore the algorithm takes a simpler form, with exact values:

```

u0 = 1; ℓ0 = 1; u1 = 4
for i = 1..n - 2 do
    ℓi = 1 / ui
    ui+1 = 4 - ℓi
end for
ℓn-1 = 0; un = 1

```

This algorithm can be looked at as a recursive formula for both ℓ_i and u_i . We

can express them as follows:

$$\ell_i = \frac{1}{4 - \ell_{i-1}} = \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \ell_{i-2}}} = \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \ell_{i-3}}}} \dots$$

$$u_i = 4 - \frac{1}{u_{i-1}} = 4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{u_{i-2}}} = 4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{u_{i-3}}}} \dots$$

If we assume for a moment that they are infinite sequences for ℓ and u as the limits:

$$\ell = \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \dots}}}$$

$$u = 4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \dots}}}$$

From now on we do not calculate u since it is $4 - \ell$. We can see that ℓ appears in it's equation:

$$\ell = \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \frac{1}{4 - \dots}}} = \frac{1}{4 - \ell}$$

We then get a quadratic equation by multiplying with $4 - \ell$:

$$-\ell^2 + 4\ell - 1 = 0$$

From which we get 2 values for ℓ :

$$\ell = \frac{4 \pm \sqrt{12}}{2} \approx \begin{cases} 0.26794919243 \\ 3.73205080757 \end{cases}$$

By calculating the first 5 ℓ_i -s, we can quickly notice that it converges to 0.26794919243 which means that in our case:

$$\ell \approx 0.26794919243$$

$$u \approx 3.73205080757$$

If we calculate ℓ_i for $1 \leq i \leq 20$ we can see that it converges very fast as i increases, after $i = 16$ even the double numerical precision is not enough to calculate the difference between ℓ_i and ℓ_{i+1} . This is the same for u_i . This means if we calculate both of them up to $i = 16$ and save the values, we can just repeat the $i = 16th$ value as many times as needed. Thus we can save n calculation processing time by

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 & b_0 & & & & 0 \\ & u_2 & b_1 & & & \\ & & u_3 & b_2 & & \\ & & & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & & u_{n-1} & b_{n-1} \\ 0 & & & & 0 & u_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c_0 \\ \vdots \\ c_{n-1} \\ c_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 \\ \vdots \\ y_{n-1} \\ y_n \end{bmatrix}$$

We can see that: $u_n c_n = y_n$ and similarly to forward elimination (just backwards), we can calculate

$$c_{n-1} = \frac{y_{n-1} - b_{n-1}c_n}{u_{n-1}}, \quad \text{then}$$

$$c_{n-2} = \frac{y_{n-2} - b_{n-2}c_{n-1}}{u_{n-2}}$$

and so on going backward from row to row. Thus we get the general equation:

$$c_i = \frac{y_i - b_i c_{i+1}}{u_i},$$

or in our case for $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$:

$$c_i = \frac{y_i - c_{i+1}}{u_i}.$$

We do not need an equation for $i = 0$, since we know the value of c_0 is zero because of the natural condition. Now we know every c_i coefficient, we already knew every a_i , and by simply substituting into (6.4) and into (6.2) we can get every b_i and d_i . Thus we know how to calculate every coefficient of the natural cubic spline.

6.2 Obstacle detection

An obstacle is any virtual object that is not the virtual twin of the robot, or the static environment, in our case it is the virtual model of the worker. In the virtual environment instead of the virtual twin of the robot, we use a bounding box representation. This is every separate part that is capable of moving (every joint). Notice in Figure 6.1.a that the virtual twin does not contain a gripper, but there is a bounding box for it in Figure 6.1.b. There is no gripper on the virtual twin because there are multiple types of grippers that can be put on the UR5. These grippers can have different dimensions, thus we made it so that the grippers's bounding box can be changed in size even when the software is running.

Figure 6.1: The Virtual twin and the bounding box representation

This bounding box representation is created in Blender with a Python script, that creates a cuboid for each joint based on its dimensions and then builds up the parent-child relations based on the original. The reason we use Blender is that the pivot points of the bounding boxes must also be changed to have a working replica of the UR5-s movements. In Blender, all this can be done with a short script, and we can export the new model, so we do not have to store the original larger file on Hololens 2. This is beneficial for us in two ways. First and foremost it requires much less computation than the virtual twin both in visualization and collision detection. Secondly, it enables the worker to see exactly what the system uses to calculate collisions, which can decrease the number of collisions simply by supplying the worker with more information, which in turn increases trust in the software. Each separate bounding box can collide with any part of the human model. The built-in algorithms in Unity detect these collisions. These simply calculate if an object's bounding box enters another's bounding box, upon which an event is called that has the information of the two colliding bodies, one of which is always part of the UR5 and the other is part of the human model.

6.3 Path planning

Path planning requires us to know where exactly can we move. It is not enough to know where the obstacle is, and what is the obstacle because the position of the obstacle is its midpoint and there can be multiple obstacles around the one we collided with. Furthermore, the robot's and the obstacle's pose changes throughout the assembly process, making it difficult to write an exact algorithm to avoid it. It is possible, but it would be computationally heavy, and since the robotic arm's base is fixed to a certain position, we can get a very efficient algorithm by checking only some predefined directions.

6.3.1 Data gathering

The aforementioned event supplies the necessary data to calculate paths in these directions. This data contains the distances of the obstacle at different points from certain planes. The planes are defined by normal vectors. We use 3 normal vectors, thus 3 planes. The first one is pointing from the base of UR5 to the obstacle.

Figure 6.2: Plane defined by vector from base to obstacle

In this case, measurements are made at h stepsize along the horizontal line at the obstacle's height. The second and third vectors are pointing straight down and up, from below and above the UR5, and measurements are taken in a line

from the gripper's midpoint. This line is the one pointing from the gripper to a synchronization point. The chosen point is the next in line if it is reachable or if it is a crucial point, in which case we cannot miss it. Otherwise, we look for the next reachable or crucial synchronization point. A synchronization point is deemed reachable if there is at least an r cm radius empty space around it, where r is the diameter of the bottom of the gripper. It is enough to calculate along these lines because as the base is fixed we know the directions the robot (the gripper) can follow:

- up/down,
- straight forward/backward the base,
- left-to-right or right-to-left,
- the combination of these.

Since we have the specific scenario of the robotic arm working together with a human on a table, we can assume that the most common movement will be sideways, and the second most common will be forward-backward. While up/down movement almost only occurs when the UR5 picks up or puts down something. Furthermore, collision with the worker can only happen in the space between the worker and the base. This leaves only 3 options for the robotic arm to avoid the obstacle:

- move above it
- move below it
- move behind it (from the perspective of the worker)

These 3 options can be examined by the measurements made from the 3 directions. To have the most efficient route we simply need to follow the original path as much as possible (since we already established that the predefined route is the best for cooperation). This we can achieve by only modifying the path to the next synchronization point, and we stay as close as possible to the original movement of the robot on the modified path.

Figure 6.3: Data collected from the 3 directions

These data points are collected by rays hitting the obstacle. We send rays from the aforementioned directions, if a ray hits an object, the distance otherwise a zero is put into the data set. To visualize this we drew red spheres to every point the ray hit. We can recover the 3D data from the direction and the distance anytime by the following equation:

$$x = rPos + rDir \cdot d$$

x is the 3D position, $rPos$ is the position from where the ray started, $rDir$ is the ray direction and d is the distance that we saved into the data set. Calculating the splines, and which path is the shortest can be done with this 2D data, and then we can convert back the splines' point to 3D. Since these points are on the surface of the obstacle (if the ray hits), it would not be possible (or would be very difficult) to move the robot along them without touching the obstacle, this can be simply solved by moving each point towards the plane from which the ray was sent. This provides us a way to include an additional safe zone around obstacles into which the robot cannot enter. In our case, we move them by $5cm$, which in addition to the safe zone included in the human model, should provide us with enough space to avoid every collision while not making the paths significantly longer. Unfortunately, if we examine Figure 6.3 we can see that data from each direction is not necessarily the distance to the object from the appropriate plane (the distance between the plane and the object's closest point to the plane). For example in Figure 6.3.b it is clear that the top of the object is not where the measurement was made, which would not be a problem if the gripper was a point, but the gripper is a cuboid, thus there is a chance that (even with the safe zone added) one of the sides still hits the obstacle. This can be seen in Figure 6.4.

(a) Bottom of the gripper at the point of hit (b) Bottom of the gripper is at the offset point (5cm elevation)

Figure 6.4: It is not enough to check the midpoint of the gripper

We need to know the obstacle's shape along a rectangular shape that is as wide as the bottom of the gripper. Fortunately, we can make 2 more measurements from each of the 3 directions, one from a corner and one from the diagonally opposite of that corner Figure 6.6. This way we get enough data for both the sideways and forward/backward movement.

Figure 6.5: Bottom of gripper, ray starting positions

We can prove that it is enough to check along these lines by calculating what shape, more precisely what angle the obstacle needs to have to be able to fit between the hitpoint and hit the bottom of the gripper, even with the 5cm safe zone added. The biggest gripper we will use is 15cm long, thus the obstacle has to be thinner

than 7.5cm , or has to have a corner that is maximum 73.74° wide as can be seen in the following image:

Figure 6.6: Bottom of gripper, ray starting positions

Since we know that the human model (apart from the hands) is built up of cylinders and a sphere (for the head) these can only hit the gripper if they can fit into the 7.5cm gap, but we know that all of these shapes are bigger than that. The hands, however, have a way of fitting into the gap, because the hand model's height with straightened-out fingers is 6cm . One easy way to solve this is to increase it to at least 8cm , but it is not necessary since to be able to avoid the rays the hand has to be perfectly aligned with the gap while the robot moves. Even if someone would like to collide this way deliberately it would be hard to achieve. On the other hand just to be safe we have increased the height to 10cm . Therefore we can conclude that the aforementioned 9 rays (3 from 3 directions) will be sufficient to avoid obstacles, and now we can see why it was important to make the spline calculations optimized.

6.3.2 Path from the data

The data we gathered is only important around the obstacle, however, there can be distance between the obstacle and the next synchronization point. There are two ways we can solve this. The first is very simple: connect the end of the obstacle linearly to the synchronization point. This will be the one we use because the acceleration of the robot does not have as much of an impact on the path as a vehicle's (for

example a drone's) would. The robotic arm will move at a constant speed whenever it can, which it can reach almost immediately. In the case of vehicles, the sudden direction change can cause them to leave the path, therefore we have to use splines to smoothen it. This will be the other method, we connect the synchronization point to the end of the obstacle by fitting a spline on them. Before we fit the spline on the data, however, we make one more modification. We change the values between the current position of the gripper and the first hitpoint of the obstacle because all of them are zeros. We could fit a spline on them, but it would cause a gripper to not change direction until it reached the obstacle. In the case of the robotic arm, it will be enough to linearly connect the current position to the first hitpoint, for the same reason as discussed before. Furthermore, we take the line from the 3 lines from each direction that is the closest to the direction's plane, thus we only have to calculate one spline from each direction but with that, we can ensure to avoid the obstacle with all parts of the gripper.

Chapter 7

Overview of the new system

The whole system can be divided into 5 parts:

- Real robot control
- Virtual robot control
- Virtual robot movement prediction
- Human model based on hand movement
- Object avoidance

At startup, the real and the virtual robot control starts to run, and immediately after that, the robot movement predictor starts. This means when the assembly starts, the robot starts to move together with the virtual robot, and a future robot shows the worker where the robot will go. If the worker starts to move, the human model predictor starts too. From the worker's point of view, a collision happens if the worker enters the hologram of the future robot in the virtual environment (or collides with the real robot). When the collision is detected, measurements are made from the 3 fixed directions, Paths are created based on these measurements which avoid the obstacle. The system switches the predefined path to the shortest of the calculated paths until the next available synchronization point is reached. Both the virtual and the real robot start to follow this new path, as well as the future robot is set to predict this new path too. (This is another addition compared to PREHUROCO, where on a collision, the future robot continued on the predefined path until a synchronization point was not reached.) Thanks to this, collisions can be predicted on the new path too, thus enabling continuous obstacle avoidance.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

Our solution can avoid obstacles in real time, sometimes even without increasing the total assembly time. In most cases, however, the new path will be longer than the predefined one, and we can only minimize the increase. There is only one situation when the time does not increase (in most cases): when we skip the synchronization point. However, we cannot assume that there always will be skippable synchronization points. Therefore there is one critical point in the system that must be improved. That is to be able to modify the path to meet the predefined times for synchronization points. We need this because there are situations when the robot cannot avoid the obstacle while being on time even if we skip a synchronization point. If that happens there are ways to get back the lost time (e.g. skipping another synchronization point or a different path). This will be the first problem to solve after the current solution has been properly tested. On the other hand, with the obstacle avoidance system, we have almost entirely eliminated the need for a total assembly line restart. Although we have not been able to test the new solution in a relevant industry environment (like PREHUROCO was tested), we can conclude that with just the new human model-based collision detection system, we have already achieved what we set out to do. Additionally, we successfully added an obstacle avoidance system, that can avoid most obstacles in our specific task, while minimizing the increase in total assembly time. This avoidance system can be greatly improved. The spline calculations could be changed to handle 3D data, and based on that more efficient routes might be found. We will examine this in the future because as we mentioned before, we intend to improve the system so we can use it for vehicles too. Furthermore, the avoidance system could be upgraded by

rewriting the inverse kinematics calculations so that they include the obstacle's area as a forbidden space. Hence the inverse kinematics itself would contain everything to control the robot. As we would like to use this solution as a base for vehicles, this option was not examined in greater detail. Altogether there were 4 problems that we wanted to solve, and we were able to solve them:

- too many parts: now only the Hololens 2 and the UR5 are needed,
- Kinect v2 has been removed: we have our new human model,
- we have added an obstacle avoidance system,
- ApertusVR has been removed: the communication between the Hololens 2 and the UR5 is done through simple TCP messages.

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